

RESONANCE TUNING OF RF DEVICES THROUGH ORIGAMI FOLDING

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ABSTRACT

Reconfigurable RF devices hold great promise as adaptive antennas, signal filters, reflectors, and ambient RF energy harvesters. Origami design techniques offer a method of precise reconfiguration through a mapping between 2D and 3D spaces defined as a series of folding operations. Leveraging these design concepts, origami patterns are used in this work as a platform for investigating electromagnetic performances of geometrically reconfigurable RF devices. Resonance characteristics of frequency selective surfaces (FSSs) were examined on periodic arrays of composed of dipole and square loop conducting elements printed on three origami tessellations, specifically a corrugated, Miura, and Waterbomb-Miura pattern. Dipoles printed on tessellations that lead to changes in separation distances exhibit resonance shift (up to 10%), with the separation in the direction orthogonal to the dipole orientations having a more significant effect. Square loops are less influenced by folding in terms of the resonance shift, however, adjacent elements start to couple to create an additional resonance at large fold. The coupling frequency is dependent on both interspacing distance between loops and the breaking of the loop plane. The results of this initial study demonstrate the relevance of origami-based approaches to the design of reconfigurable EM devices with multifunctionality, such as frequency tuning and configuration-dependent dual frequencies. Future investigation into the design of new origami patterns and conductive trace combinations for EM applications is motivated by these findings.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reconfigurable design approaches for RF devices, such as antennas, sensors, reflectors, and ambient RF energy harvesters, would enable tunable multifunctionality and allow for the accommodation of varying operating conditions and performance requirements. Existing tuning strategies for RF devices rely largely on circuit tuning strategies, such as including varactor diodes [1-3] or adjusting lumped states of other electric components [4]. As discussed in a recent review by Turpin et al, geometric tuning approaches present an attractive alternative to circuit tuning due to the strong effect of the shape of the conducting elements and their orientations on the resonance characteristics [5]. However, many of the strategies to control the geometric reconfiguration have focused on high frequency applications such as the use of MEMS in infrared and terahertz regimes [6,7] and thermal actuation of a bimetallic cantilevers for terahertz applications [8], in part due to the range of motions attainable through these systems. Origami is well suited as a platform for geometric RF tuning due to its precise mapping between 2D (crease pattern) to 3D (folded geometry) configurations and the additional fabrication convenience of possessing an initial 2D state. Folding concepts have already been used for tuning mechanical, acoustic and electromagnetic properties [9-11], where the desired properties are achieved through the geometric redistribution of constituent materials.

Despite the wide range of potential applications of origami in electromagnetics, the literature on origami EM systems is limited. A few examples include a resonance tuning of frequency selective surfaces (FSSs) through folding the substrate in a Miura-ori pattern [11], a helical antenna design based on an origami spring [12], and curved corrugated sheets for tunable antenna design [13]. With the recent development of diverse stimuli responsive materials for hinge-like actuation [14], fold-based design strategies for geometric tuning will likely expand. However, a unique challenge of designing these systems is the complex relationship between the geometric configurations and the EM interactions of constituent components. This limits the intuition on what designs may work, motivating an initial investigation of a survey of origami pattern and conductive element combinations. This paper investigates simple FSS designs combined with a collection of known origami tessellations, in order to improve the fundamental understanding of the effects of folding on resonating EM devices towards the development of a systematic design method. Although the performance investigation is focused on the resonance characteristics of FSSs, other properties such as the efficiency, gain, radiation patterns are expected to be influenced by folding and would be important factors to consider in design of many other RF devices.

2 ANALYSIS METHOD

Analysis of each FSS design is carried out by combining the rigid origami simulation [15] and the finite element method in the frequency domain using COMSOL RF Module. Fold patterns considered here are thin substrates folded as origami tessellations and decorated with arrays of conducting elements. Only tessellations that remain globally planar are considered in order to enable Cartesian periodic boundary conditions for the EM analysis. Key assumptions for the EM simulation include: 1) substrate is assumed to be a very thin dielectric ($\ll 0.01\lambda$) with negligible effect in the range of frequencies of interest, and 2) conducting prints are assumed to be lossless. These assumptions would necessarily require modification for actual device design, but are adequate for the goal of this study, which is to understand the underlying principles of tuning phenomenon in folded EM components.

2.1 Rigid origami simulation

Three origami tessellations are constructed from basic crease pattern units shown in Figure 1(a) for this study. A repetition of parallel lines make a corrugation and alternating mountain-based and valley-based spherical 4-bar mechanism units produce the Miura-ori as shown in Figure 1(b). Two variations, derived by combining 4-bar mechanisms and parallel line units in a way that tessellates the sheet while keeping the overall curvature of the folded origami tessellation to zero, are shown in Figure 1(b). The folding these tessellations in the simulation are carried out using the rigid origami model that traces isometric mapping with no elastic deformations (stretching or bending of facets and foldlines). The governing equation for the rigid origami simulation for general multiple vertex origami was introduced by Tachi [15], which is based upon the condition of foldability presented by belcastro and Hull in [16]. The crease pattern is described through the connectivity of vertices and sector angles; the fold motion is described using dihedral or fold angles as state variables. Snapshots of the fold simulation of tessellations composed of 4x4 units of periodicity are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Crease patterns used for tessellations. (a) Basic units used to construct tessellations; (b) periodic units of tessellations. (red – mountain, blue – valley)

Figure 2: 3D configurations of tessellations simulated using the rigid origami model ([15, 16])

2.2 Electromagnetics of origami

The information on the geometric configurations and their transformations through folding is stored in the form of vertex connectivity and vertex coordinates. This data is used to draw conducting elements in COMSOL using LiveLink with Matlab for each configuration and each design. The two conducting prints shown in Figure 3 (a) are drawn inside of a computational domain as shown in Figure 3(c).

Figure 3: Conducting elements printed on each basic crease pattern unit and the geometry drawn within the computational domain in the FEM setup

The vector Helmholtz formulation of Maxwell's equations

$$\nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu_r} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) - k_0^2 \epsilon_r \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad (1)$$

is solved for the electric field \mathbf{E} . Vacuum is assumed as the medium within the computational domain, with relative permittivity ϵ_r and relative permeability μ_r set to 1. Similarly, k_0 corresponds to the vacuum wavenumber. The simulation is done only on the unit of periodicity and Bloch-Floquet periodic BCs are used at $x = 0, L_x$ surfaces and $y = 0, L_y$ surfaces as:

$$\mathbf{E}(x + L_x, y + L_y, z) = \mathbf{E}(x, y, z) \exp(-j\mathbf{k} \cdot (L_x \hat{i} + L_y \hat{j})) \quad (2)$$

where $j = \sqrt{-1}$. The conducting elements are approximated as perfect electric conductors (PEC), which is modelled as

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is a unit vector normal to the surfaces, i.e., the tangential component of the electric field at the PEC surfaces is zero. Each port is excited by a dominant eigenmode with the electric field polarization specified by a constant vector

$$\mathbf{E}_0 = [\cos\theta \cos\phi, \cos\theta \sin\phi, -\sin\theta]^T \quad (4)$$

To truncate the computational domain towards spaces above and below the FSS, perfectly matched layers (PMLs) and absorbing boundary conditions (ABCs) are used. The electric field distribution found by solving Eq. (1) is then used to compute the reflection and transmission coefficients, S_{11} and S_{21} as

$$S_{11} = \frac{\int_{\Gamma_{port1}} (E - E_1) \cdot E_1^*}{\int_{\Gamma_{port1}} E_1 \cdot E_1^*}, \quad S_{21} = \frac{\int_{\Gamma_{port2}} E \cdot E_2^*}{\int_{\Gamma_{port2}} E_2 \cdot E_2^*} \quad (5)$$

where E_1 and E_2 refer to the excitation modes at ports 1 and 2, respectively, and \mathbf{E} is the computed electric field and \mathbf{E}^* denotes the complex conjugate. The magnitudes of the S-parameters are converted to the dB scale as $|S| [dB] = 20 \log_{10} |S|$ and plotted over a range of frequencies to examine the resonant behavior of each design.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The parameters shown in Table 1 are used to specify the conducting prints drawn in Figure 3. These patterns are used to decorate the tessellations in Figure 2.

Table 1: Geometric parameters used in the simulation of prints (Figure 3).

Parameter	L	w_1	d_1	l_1	w_2	d_2	l_2
Value	20cm	8mm	25mm	95mm	8mm	25mm	150mm

3.1 Polarization and surface current at resonance

Results presented in [11] shows that the change in the separation distance between adjacent conducting elements during the folding motion leads to a shift in resonance frequency. Investigation of this phenomenon may be simplified by looking at resonating dipoles printed on a corrugation that alters the separation distance as the substrate is folded. The design in Figure 3 (a) has two sets of dipoles oriented along the x - and y -directions. When this pattern is excited with the electric field polarized along the x -direction ($\theta = 0, \phi = 0$), the two dipoles aligned in the x -direction exhibit a current flow at the resonant frequency, as shown in Figure 4 (a). An equivalent circuit at this polarization depicted in Figure 4 (c) is an LC circuit with an assumption of no resistive loss [17]. A similar phenomenon is observed when the substrate is folded, creating folds in the excited dipoles (Figure 4 (b)). When the pattern is

excited with a rotated polarization with $\phi = \pi/2$, the other two dipoles experience a current flow as shown in Figure 4 (d,e), resulting in the same equivalent circuit as before but aligned along the y-direction (Figure 4 (f)).

Figure 4: Surface current density on dipoles at orthogonal polarizations. Color plot range Blue 0 – Red 20 [A/m].

Similar surface current plots can be produced for the square loop design in Figure 3 (b). At resonance, the segments aligned with the electric field direction are excited as before (Figure 5 (a,d)). A similar surface current distribution is observed when the loop is folded along the centerline (Figure 5 (b,e)). The equivalent circuit in this case has two parallel inductors [17] connected through the segments of the conductor orthogonal to the electric field direction (Figure 5 (c,f)).

Figure 5: Surface current density on square loops at orthogonal polarizations. Color plot range Blue 0 – Red 10 [A/m].

3.2 Tessellation patterns and resonance shift

The frequency at which the dipoles are excited depends on many factors including the print geometry and the placement of the prints. The frequency sweeps of the transmission coefficients are plotted in Figure 6 for four different corrugated fold configurations indicated by time step t . The resonance is observed at 1.38GHz at the initial flat state ($t=1$) for both polarizations $\phi = 0$ and $\phi = \pi/2$, reflecting the design's 4-fold rotational symmetry. However, the symmetry is broken once the pattern is folded, and different resonance characteristics are observed. Similarly to the results reported in [11], the resonance shifts upward as the separation distance becomes smaller with folding. In the case of the x -polarization ($\phi = 0$), the change in the separation distance is along the direction parallel to the excited dipoles, while the separation changes in the orthogonal direction to the excited dipoles for the y -

polarization ($\phi = \pi/2$). The resonance shift is larger for the y -polarization (7.3%) compared to the x -polarization case (1.6%). The difference in frequency shifts with polarization demonstrates how the multiple tuning sensitivities can be designed into a single origami substrate with the appropriate symmetries. It further highlights that other fold patterns may lead to unique resonance characteristics as the conductive elements separate during the fold evolution.

Figure 6: Transmission coefficients for dipoles printed on a corrugation

When dipoles are printed on the Miura-ori, separation in both x - and y -directions become smaller as the substrate is folded, and the y -projection of the tessellation shrinks as the tessellation corrugates along the x -direction. As a result, resonances plotted in Figure 7 (b) exhibit an upward shift of 8.3%. Similar behavior with a larger upward resonance shift of 10.6% is observed in a tessellation composed of Miura-ori and waterbomb shown in Figure 8(a). These results are summarized in Figure 9, indicating a consistent trend of upward resonance shift with a shrinkage of the projection dimensions (see Tab.2).

Figure 7: Transmission coefficients for dipoles and square loops on Miura-ori

Figure 8: Transmission coefficients for dipoles and square loops on Miura-ori + waterbomb tessellation

Figure 9: Resonances

Table 2: The evolution of the projected dimensions of the three tessellations.

Pattern	t = 1 ($L_x = L$)	t = 10 ($L_x = 0.98L$)	t = 20 ($L_x = 0.92L$)	t = 30 ($L_x = 0.81L$)
Corrugation	L_y	L_y	L_y	L_y
Miura-ori	L_y	$0.99L_y$	$0.95L_y$	$0.9L_y$
Miura-ori + waterbomb	L_y	$0.97L_y$	$0.87L_y$	$0.74L_y$

Square loops printed on the Miura-ori exhibit a very small shift (2.4%) in resonance as seen in Figure 7 (c). A possible explanation for this is because the location of the resonance in loops is primarily determined by its circumference, and coupling effects from the separation distance does not significantly shift the dominant frequency. A small resonance shift (3.7%) is observed in the square loops printed on the Miura+waterbomb tessellations in Figure 8 (c), which is consistent with the observation with Miura-ori. However, in both the Miura (Figure 7(c)) and Miura+waterbomb geometries (Figure 8 (c)), an extra resonance appears at a lower frequency towards large fold ($t= 20, 30$ simulations). As this is not observed in square loops printed on corrugation, nor in the fold configurations near the flat state, the effect is hypothesized to be a consequence of adjacent elements coupling along the y -separation distance (fixed

in corrugated pattern) and deformation of the loops from planar to bent configurations. A series of numerical experiments were performed to isolate the coupling mechanism responsible for this lower frequency resonance.

Figure 10: Numerical experiments to isolate the effect creating the lower resonance

The study was conducted with the Miura-ori at the $t=30$ configuration. As the substrate with square loop prints is folded in Miura-ori pattern, several geometric alterations to the conducting square loops occur: 1) the separation distance between the adjacent loops becomes smaller; 2) the dihedral angle between the mean planes hosting the adjacent loops becomes smaller; 3) bends are introduced on the conductive trace. As shown in Figure 10 (a-c) none of the geometric changes, isolated as described above, reproduced the additional lower resonance. However, when two adjacent loops folded along Miura-ori are simulated (instead of four loops used in other simulations following the unit of periodicity indicated in Figure 1 (b)), the lower resonance appeared. This indicates that the lower resonance is a result of creating bends on the loops and coupling of elements along the y -direction.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The potential of origami fold patterns as geometric tuning mechanisms for EM resonances was investigated in this study. Numerical simulations were carried out on three periodic fold geometries and two conductive element patterns to study the effect of folding on the frequency existence and shift in FSSs. This is not a comprehensive survey, but the selections are relevant as the fold patterns and conductive elements are some of the most common within the origami design and FSS communities, respectively. In the dipole systems, shifts in resonance ($\sim 10\%$) were observed when the element separation distances are tuned along the direction orthogonal to the dipole orientations. The shift is smaller than previously reported resonance tuning through a geometric approach using split ring resonators (33% [18]). However, larger shifts in resonance are anticipated in the current origami patterns as the structures are folded towards closure. Reorientation of the printed FSS components or repolarization of the electric field was also shown as a way to narrow the sensitivity of the frequency tuning (i.e. 1.5% vs 7.3% shift depending on polarization). In contrast, square loops exhibited a smaller shift in resonance with folding, but an additional resonance, not observed with the dipoles, appears for Miura-ori and Mira-ori+waterbomb patterns at larger folded configurations. A series of numerical tests were conducted to form a hypothesis that this phenomenon is due to the combined effect of bending along the conductive traces and coupling of adjacent elements.

The results show that there are various mechanisms that cause changes in resonance characteristics of folded FSSs and motivate further investigation of a diverse combination of prints and folding patterns. In addition, the variety of resonance coupling and tuning capability demonstrated with origami substrates also motivates the development of design tools to predict the optimal fold patterns and conductive patterns for specific EM performance criteria.

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